

Period of Induction in Chemical Reactions: Action of Hypophosphorous Acid on Copper Salts.

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It has been shown that period of induction is not confined to photochemical reactions, but is observable in several other reactions such as the action of acids on zinc, action of nitric acid on copper, action of acids on thiosulphates, and action of sulphurous acid on iodic acid. Recently Neogi and Neogi (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 131, 30) have studied the period of induction in the interaction of mercuric chloride and sodium bicarbonate. Whilst preparing cuprous hydride by the interaction of hypophosphorous acid on copper sulphate, we observed that a distinct period of induction existed in this chemical reaction. Such a period was also observed in the case of the action of hypophosphorous acid on cupric chloride. It was, therefore, considered desirable to study these two instances of induction thoroughly.

It is to be noted at the commencement that no single cause can be uniformly assigned to all chemical reactions in which a period of induction can be observed. In the case of the action of hydrogen and chlorine, Chapmann and his co-workers (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, 74, 400; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1399, and subsequent papers) have shown that minute traces of impurities are an important factor in causing the period of induction. So far as the interaction of sulphurous acid on iodic acid is concerned, Landolt (*Ber.*, 1886, 19, 1317) has shown that the period of induction is due to successive intermediate reactions, which take place before iodine is finally liberated. Neogi and Neogi (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the period of induction in the interaction of sodium bicarbonate and mercuric chloride is similarly due to the formation of several intermediate compounds.

Now turning to the reactions under examination, the formation of cuprous hydride, by the interaction of hypophosphorous acid on copper sulphate, can never be due to the occurrence of a single reaction. The action of hypophosphorous acid on cupric chloride has also been shown here to be not merely a case of reduction of the cupric chloride to cuprous chloride, but really due to the formation of unstable intermediate compounds. It is, therefore, natural to presume that the period of induction in these cases

is mainly, if not solely, due to the formation of unstable intermediate compounds formed in successive reactions which take time before a visible reaction is observed. The nature of these intermediate reactions would be discussed later on.

As regards the end products of the interaction between copper sulphate and hypophosphorous acid, Wurtz (*Compt. rend.*, 1844, 18, 102) obtained cuprous hydride by treating the mixture below 70°. Bartlett and Merrill (*Amer. J. Sci.*, 1895, 17, 195) also obtained the same hydride in a similar manner. Berthelot has stated that the hydride contains some basic cuprous phosphate as an impurity. Vorländer and Mayer obtained cuprous hydride by the action of sodium hyposulphite solution and dilute sulphuric acid on copper sulphate solution. Very recently Muller and Bradely (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1669) have shown the undoubted existence of cuprous hydride, CuH.

As regards the end product of the action of hypophosphorous acid on cupric chloride, existing literature states that cuprous chloride is precipitated on warming. We have, however, prepared pure cuprous hypophosphite solution, which on simple heating yields cuprous hydride, but with excess of cupric chloride yields cuprous chloride. We are of opinion that the formation of cuprous chloride by the interaction of hypophosphorous acid on cupric chloride is not merely a case of reduction of the cupric chloride, but really a product of decomposition through stages to be discussed later on.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Hypophosphorous Acid on Copper Sulphate.—Standard solutions containing known weights of copper sulphate and hypophosphorous acid were prepared. The strength of the hypophosphorous acid was ascertained by the iodine method (Sutton, "Volumetric Analysis," p. 317).

A measured volume of each solution, usually 10 c. c., was taken into two 50 c. c. boiling tubes of the same size and kept immersed in a thermostat and heated up to the temperature of the bath. The thermostat was often replaced by a water-bath, the water being contained in a capacious beaker (800 c. c.) and heated to the requisite temperature, which was maintained practically constant by means of a microburner. This is an excellent substitute for a thermostat, as the temperature could be kept within $\pm 1^\circ$. The test tube containing the hypophosphorous acid solution was taken out from the bath and

the contents rapidly poured into the copper sulphate solution. By means of a standardised and thoroughly reliable stop-watch, the period of induction was read out, until a precipitate was just visible. The mixture was stirred only once every time by means of the thermometer dipped into the copper sulphate solution. A large amount of practice and repeated trials would be necessary in order to ensure the correct reading and the particular shade of the colour of the mixture, when the first visible reaction is observed. A dark background was used so that the required shade of the colour would be correctly read out each time.

The strength of the copper sulphate as well as of the acid solution was varied by taking measured volumes of their concentrated standard solutions and adding the requisite quantity of water. Readings of the stop-watch were taken after at first keeping the strength of the acid solution constant and varying the strength of the copper sulphate solution. The reversed process was also experimented upon. Lastly the strengths of both the acid and the sulphate were varied.

Period of Induction in the Action of Hypophosphorous Acid on Cupric Chloride.

The period of induction in the interaction of cupric chloride and hypophosphorous acid, when cuprous chloride is precipitated, was next studied in detail. The results were similar to those obtained in the case of copper sulphate. Both sets of results are given side by side in each of the following tables.

TABLE I.

C_{Cu} = concentration of copper sulphate or chloride in gram. moles per litre. C_H = concentration of the acid.

Temperature = 70°. T = Induction period. $K = \frac{T - T_1}{C_1 - 1}$.

Copper sulphate. $C_H = 0.5023$.			Cupric chloride. $C_H = 0.4812$.		
C_{Cu}	T (sec.)	K.	C_{Cu}	T (sec.)	K
0.0833	18	—	0.1667	35	—
0.0632	25	20.6	0.1429	43	48.4
0.0500	31	19.5	0.1334	47.5	50.0
0.0417	39	21.0	0.1250	51	47.9
0.0385	41.5	20.0	0.1177	55.5	49.2
0.0357	45	20.2	0.1112	60	50.0
0.0333	48	21.2	0.1053	63.5	48.9
0.0312	52	20.3	0.1000	67	47.9
0.0294	55	20.1	0.0953	71	48.0
0.0289	59	21.8	0.0909	75	47.8
	Mean	20.5		Mean	49.7

It would be observed from the above table that when the strength of the copper sulphate was getting weaker, the strength of the acid remaining constant, the period of induction was increasing, so much so that with $C_{\text{Cu}}=0.0289$, the period of induction was three times as much as that when $C_{\text{Cu}}=0.0833$. A similar result was obtained in the case of cupric chloride.

No simple proportionality as that of inverse ratio, however, is observable but an equation of the following nature can be worked out :-

$$T - T_1 = K \left(\frac{C_1}{C} - 1 \right) \quad \text{or} \quad K = \frac{T - T_1}{\frac{C_1}{C} - 1}$$

where C_1 and T_1 are initial concentration and the corresponding period of induction. The nature of K is the same in subsequent tables.

TABLE II.

Temperature = 70°

Copper sulphate. $C_{\text{Cu}}=0.2500$.			Cupric chloride. $C_{\text{Cu}}=0.5002$.		
C_{H}	T (sec.)	K .	C_{H}	T (sec.)	K .
0.5023	13	—	0.1925	275	—
0.4186	23	50.1	0.1782	342	835
0.3588	34	52.5	0.1718	375	829
0.3139	44	51.1	0.1659	408	829
0.2955	49	51.4	0.1604	440	825
0.2790	55	52.4	0.1552	474	827
0.2644	63	53.6	0.1504	512	846
0.2551	66	53.0	0.1458	540	828
0.2392	70	51.8	0.1415	574	829
0.2283	76	52.4	0.1375	613	845
		Mean			Mean
		51.9			832

TABLE III.
Copper Salts and Hypophosphorous Acid.
Temperature = 70°.

Copper sulphate.				Cupric chloride.			
C_H .	C_{Cu} .	T (secs.)	K .	C_{Cu} .	C_H .	T (secs.)	K .
0.5023	0.2500	13	—	0.5002	0.4812	50	—
0.4186	0.2083	18	25.0	0.3573	0.3437	78	70.0
0.3588	0.1786	24	27.5	0.3126	0.3007	92	70.0
0.3139	0.1562	29	26.6	0.2779	0.2673	105	68.7
0.2790	0.1389	34	26.2	0.2501	0.2406	118	68.0
0.2511	0.1250	40	27.0	0.2274	0.2187	130	71.9
0.2392	0.1190	42	26.3	0.2084	0.2005	145	67.8
0.2233	0.1137	45	26.7	0.1924	0.1851	158	67.5
0.2184	0.1087	48	26.9	0.1788	0.1718	170	66.8
0.2098	0.1042	51	27.1	0.1667	0.1604	185	67.6
		Mean	26.6			Mean	69.7

Fig. 1.

I = Copper sulphate. II = Cupric chloride

The effect of temperature on the period of induction was next studied, the solution being heated in a thermostat. With increasing temperature the period of induction decreases.

TABLE IV.

Copper sulphate.

$$C_{Cu} = 0.2500. C_H = 0.2511.$$

Temp.	...	50°	60°	70°	80°
T	...	53	27	13	6.5 secs

$$C_{Cu} = 0.5000. C_H = 0.2511.$$

Temp.	...	50°	60°	70°	80°
T	...	66	40	24	13.5 secs.

$$C_{Cu} = 0.1250. C_H = 0.5022.$$

Temp.	...	50°	60°	70°	80°
T	...	40	18	9	4 secs.

Cupric chloride.

$$C_{Cu} = 0.5002. C_H = 0.4814.$$

Temp.	...	50°	60°	70°	80°
T	...	50	25	13	7 secs.

If the temperature be plotted against the logarithm of the period of induction, it is found that the points obtained can all be joined by means of a straight line (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2.

I = Copper sulphate. II = Cupric chloride.

The action of alcohols on the period of induction was next studied. A measured volume of alcohol was first added to the copper salt solution, the test tube being provided with a small spiral condenser, and heated to the requisite temperature in the bath. The condenser was then disconnected and the acid also previously heated to the same temperature in the bath was quickly poured and the condenser refitted.

It would be seen from the results tabled below that the period of induction increases with the addition of increasing volumes of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl and isopropyl alcohols. In the case of the two propyl alcohols, the period of induction is almost the same when equal volumes of the two alcohols are added. This fact is of interest in view of the observations of Neogi and Neogi (*loc. cit.*) regarding the period of induction in the interaction of sodium bicarbonate and mercuric chloride, when very wide divergences in the action of the two isomeric alcohols were observed.

TABLE V.

Copper sulphate.

Temperature = 50°.

Ethyl alcohol	0	1	2	4	6	8	10 c.c.
<i>T</i>	70	88	90	95	102.5	115	135 secs.
Methyl alcohol	1	2	4	6	8	10 c.c.	
<i>T</i>	86	89	93	99	107	121 secs.	
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	1	2	4 c.c.				
<i>T</i>	87	93	95 secs.				
<i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol		...	1	2	4 c.c.				
<i>T</i>	90	92	94 secs.				

Cupric chloride.
 $C_{Cu} = 0.5002$. $C_H = 0.4812$. Temp. = 70°.

Methyl alcohol	...	0	2	4	6	8	10 c.c.
<i>T</i>	...	50	54	59	60	60	60 secs.
Ethyl alcohol	...	2	4	6	8	10 c.c.	
<i>T</i>	...	54	63	75	79	80 secs.	
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	...	2	6 c.c.				
<i>T</i>	...	54	71 secs.				
<i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol		2	6 c.c.				
<i>T</i>	...	53	73 secs.				

A little turbidity is produced by the addition of ethyl alcohol to the cupric chloride solution, which, however, disappears on the addition of the hypophosphorous acid.

The addition of different salts in the reacting mixture gave the following results.

Fig. 3.

I = Copper sulphate. II = Cupric chloride.

On a study of the action of acids on the period of induction, it was found that hydrochloric acid gives a white precipitate of cuprous chloride, hence the action of sulphuric acid and nitric acid was studied. It was found that dilute acids cause an increase, while stronger acids cause a diminution in the period of induction.

TABLE VI.

Copper sulphate.

$$C_{Cu} = 0.29000. \quad C_H = 0.2009.$$

Nitric acid (0.118N)	...	0	2	4	6	8	10 c.c.
<i>T</i> (at 50°)	...	70	80	90	101	112	120 sec.
Nitric acid (0.8501N)	...		2	4	6	8	10 c.c.
<i>T</i> (at 50°)	...		55	48	46	45	45 sec.
Sulphuric acid (0.114N)	...		2	4	6	8	10 c.c.
<i>T</i> (at 50°)	...		81	90	100	110	122 sec.

TABLE VII.

Cupric chloride.

$$C_{Cu} = 0.5002. \quad C_H = 0.4812. \quad \text{Temp.} = 70^\circ.$$

Nitric acid (0.867N)	...	0	2	4	6	8	10 c.c.
<i>T</i>	...	50	86	90	29	80	29 secs.
Hydrochloric acid (0.867N)	2	2	4	6	8	10 c.c.	
<i>T</i>	...	4	42	40	43	42	secs.
Nitric acid (0.1 N)	...	0	2	4	6	8	c.c.
<i>T</i>	...	73	82	91	101	108	secs.

Fig. 4.
I = Cu SO_4 , II = Cu Cl_2 .

after 15 minutes, using 0.478 gms. The temperature was kept at 50° and equimolecular quantities of sodium and potassium salts were employed.

TABLE VII.
Temperature = 70° .

Copper sulphate.			Cupric chloride.		
$C_{\text{Cu}} = 0.2000$, $C_{\text{H}} = 0.2009$.			$C_{\text{Cu}} = 0.5000$; $C_{\text{H}} = 0.4812$.		
Salts.		Period of induction.	Salt.		Period of induction.
0	gm.	53 secs.	0 gm.	KNO_3	50 secs.
0.818	K_2SO_4	130	0.646	„	53.5
0.659	Na_2SO_4	135			

Neogi and Neogi (*loc. cit.*) found that in the case of sodium bicarbonate and mercuric chloride, the period of induction is influenced by the presence of salts. They, however, found that the influence on the period of induction is due to the anions and is independent of the cations. The same fact was observed by Berczeller (*Z. Biol.*, 1916, 2, 444) in the case of the action of sulphurous and iodic acids and is observed in this case also as the results recorded below will show. The similarity in the observation in all these three cases leads to the conclusion that the period of induction is due to anions and not to cations of a dissolved salt. Sulphates, nitrates, chlorides, citrates and tartrates were experimented upon and found to increase the period of induction. In the case of sodium chloride, a white precipitate of cuprous chloride was obtained and in the case of sodium citrate no precipitate was obtained even

TABLE VIII—*contd.*

<i>Salts.</i>	<i>Period of induction.</i>	<i>Salts.</i>	<i>Period of induction.</i>
1·589 gm. KNO_3	143 secs.	0·537 gm. NaNO_3	53 secs.
1·322 NaNO_3	140	0·820 KCl	80
0·139 KCl	172	0·635 NaCl	84
0·107 NaCl	170	0·875 K_2SO_4	80
0·757	„ No ppt. even after 30 mins.	0·714 Na_2SO_4	83
0·118	Na-tartrate 90		
0·0915	Na-citrate 135		
0·478	„ No ppt. even after 15 mins.		
0·242	„ The appearance of the ppt. begins at 85 secs. and is complete by 120 sec.		

Potassium and sodium oxalates as well as sodium tartrate produce turbidity to the solution. As sodium oxalate gives a precipitate with copper sulphate solution it was not used.

TABLE IX.

Temperature = 50°.

<i>Copper sulphate.</i>		<i>Cupric chloride.</i>	
$C_{\text{Cu}} = 0\cdot2000. C_{\text{H}} = 0\cdot2009.$		$C = \text{cu}0\cdot5002. C_{\text{H}} = 0\cdot4812.$	
<i>Substance.</i>	<i>Period of induction.</i>	<i>Substance.</i>	<i>Period of induction.</i>
0 c.c. glycerine	53 secs.	0 c. c. glycerine	73 secs.
4 „ „	88	5 „ „	80
6 „ „	95	0·2176 gm. glucose	105
0·3095 gm. glucose	80	0·2076 „ mannose	93
0·3096 „ mannose	83	0·2076 „ cane sugar	73

As regards the action of organic substances such as glycerine and sugars, it was found that cane sugar has no effect on the period of induction, whilst glycerine, glucose and mannose increase it. In the case of fructose, the appearance of the precipitate of cuprous hydride could not be detected owing to the dark green colour produced. In the case of fructose the appearance of the precipitate was not sharp.

Action of Light on the Reactions.

With a view to test whether the present reactions are photo-chemical or not, the experiments which were originally done in diffused light were repeated in a dark room provided throughout with red glass doors and windows. The electric lamps in the room were also covered with red glass covers. Solutions of copper sulphate, or chloride and hypophosphorous acid were prepared in the dark room itself and kept there for three days. The period of induction was noted after some trials in order to adjust vision in red light when the point at which precipitation commenced could be sharply read out with the help of a stop-watch and found to be the same in the dark and in different light. As the results are for comparison only, the concentrations of the acid have been only approximately determined.

TABLE X.

Copper Sulphate and Hypophosphorous Acid.

$$C_{cv} = 0.2500.$$

C_H	T (Dark room).	T (Diffused light).
0.3100 (approx.)	47 secs.	49 secs.
0.2709 ,,	64.5	64

Cupric Chloride and Hypophosphorous Acid.

$$C_{cv} = 0.5002.$$

0.4800 (approx.)	50 secs.	50 secs.
0.3600 ,,	100	102

Intermediate Stages in both the Reactions.

As regards the action of hypophosphorous acid on copper sulphate it has already been pointed out that cuprous hydride is formed below 80° . As the formation of such a simple compound as cuprous hydride by the interaction of copper sulphate and hypophosphorous acid could not evidently take place in one stage, we were at considerable pains to ascertain, if possible, the several stages through which

the reaction must proceed. We have been able to establish that copper hypophosphite is undoubtedly an intermediate product. In fact Wurtz supposed that copper hypophosphite remains in solution when hypophosphorous acid acts on copper sulphate.

We first attempted to prepare copper hypophosphite in a pure state. Silver hypophosphite, being very unstable, thallium hypophosphite, which has hitherto been unknown, was prepared by the interaction of hypophosphorous acid and thallos carbonate (separate communication). By the subsequent double decomposition between cupric chloride and thallium hypophosphite, copper hypophosphite was obtained in a pure condition in the solution, thallos chloride being precipitated. The solution, however, on concentration in a vacuum desiccator, decomposed and copper hypophosphite was therefore not obtained in a solid condition. The solution of copper hypophosphite, however, when heated alone to 70° — 80° yielded a precipitate of cuprous hydride and when heated with cupric chloride yielded a white precipitate of cuprous chloride.

Preparation of pure Copper Hypophosphite Solution.—One gm. of thallium hypophosphite was dissolved in water and cupric chloride solution was added drop by drop, the mixture being thoroughly shaken. Thallos chloride was precipitated and when the mixture was vigorously shaken, the supernatant liquid became clear. The cupric chloride solution was added until the last drop did not produce any precipitate. The solution contained pure cuprous hypophosphite.

Pure copper hypophosphite solution was also prepared by double decomposition of recrystallised barium hypophosphite and copper sulphate when insoluble barium sulphate precipitated out and a solution of pure copper hypophosphite was obtained. The double decomposition of thallium hypophosphite and cupric chloride is to be preferred as a method of preparing pure copper hypophosphite solution as barium sulphate in the cold is very difficult to filter, and passes through the filter paper.

Decomposition of Copper Hypophosphite.—The solution of copper hypophosphite when gently heated in a water-bath at 70° — 80° yielded the cuprous hydride in the same manner as the interaction of copper sulphate and hypophosphorous acid. Again, this solution of copper hypophosphite, when gently heated with cupric chloride solution, yielded a white precipitate of cuprous chloride in the same manner as in the interaction of cupric chloride and hypophosphorous acid.

In both cases a period of induction was observed as in the case when the free hypophosphorous acid was used.

It would thus be observed that copper hypophosphite $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_2)_2$ is an intermediate product in either of the two reactions, *viz.*, the action of hypophosphorous acid on copper sulphate and copper chloride.

We have further supposed that $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_2)_2$ is then decomposed into $\text{CuH}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_2)$ and H_3PO_3 , as a result of the study of the p_{H} values of the solution. This copper hydrogen hypophosphite in the case of the copper sulphate yields CuH and in the case of cupric chloride, Cu_2Cl_2 . The reactions are represented below:—

In the case of copper sulphate—

In the case of cupric chloride—

Hypophosphorous acid is not a weak acid as was originally supposed. Though it acts as a monobasic acid the degree of its ionisation is quite high. Moreover as the reactions proceed with the ultimate precipitation of copper either as hydride or chloride, the forward reaction proceeds to the end.

Hydrogen Ion Concentration of a Solution of Copper Hypophosphite at 70°.

With a view to observe the process of the chemical reaction within the period of induction, the p_{H} value of the solution was determined. The method employed was a colorometric one, the electrometric method being not practicable as it requires a large interval of time between two determinations.

A solution of cupric hypophosphite was prepared; as this does not decompose at the ordinary temperature of the laboratory, the time necessary for filtration does not affect the period of induction.

The p_{H} values were known from the standard curves giving the relation between p_{H} values and different buffer mixtures

(Evers, *Analyst*, 1921, 46, 397). The buffer solutions used by us were 0.1 N-sodium citrate and 0.1N-hydrochloric acid.

Twenty c.c. of each of the following solutions were mixed together and the precipitate was filtered out in Gooch crucibles. Thirty c.c. of the filtered solution were heated up to 60° in a thermostat and the p_H values were determined and 2 c.c. were drawn up each time and immediately chilled to arrest further reaction and then brought to the room temperature by rubbing the test-tube. In front of it was placed another test-tube containing one c.c. of the solution without the indicator in order to compensate for the colour of the solution.

TABLE XI.

$$C_{Cu} = 0.5020. \quad C_{Ba} = 0.2501.$$

Time (min.)	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	65	70	75	77	79	81	
p_H	...	3.75	3.50	3.25	3.00	2.79	2.65	2.38	2.25	2.16	2.05	1.95	1.75	1.50

$$C_{Cu} = 0.5020. \quad C_{Ba} = 0.3002.$$

Time (min.)	0	10	20	30	40	45	50	55	60	62	64	65	66.5	
p_H	..	3.50	3.35	2.92	2.62	2.36	2.25	2.12	2.00	1.90	1.83	1.75	1.62	1.59

Ten c.c. of $CuCl_2$ (0.5002 mol.) were added to 20 c.c. of a saturated solution of lead hypophosphite at 26°. The whole thing was cooled down to 0° and was filtered cold. 25 C.c. of the filtered solution were then heated to 70° and p_H values determined.

TABLE XII.

Time (min.)	...	0	2	4	6	7	8	8.30	9	9.30	9.45
p_H	...	3.1	2.85	2.57	2.25	2.15	2.00	1.90	1.75	1.44	1.25

Fig. 5.

From the nature of the curves obtained by plotting the p_{H} values of both the reactions, which are similar to each other, it is seen that the upper part of the curves, which are of the nature of inclined straight lines, represents the stage in which phosphorous acid is produced whilst the lower part, in which the p_{H} values rapidly diminish, represents the stage at which the phosphoric acid is formed. This conclusively shows that the stages in which the two reactions have been shown to occur as exemplified in the equations given on page 542 are real ones. The precipitation comes up towards the very end of the inclined upper curve.

Discussion.

The following facts have been established in this paper, as a result of the study of the action of hypophosphorous acid on copper sulphate and of the same acid on cupric chloride.

(1) The period of induction depends on the concentration of the solutions, higher dilutions causing an increase in the period of induction.

(2) The period of induction decreases with rise of temperature.

(3) It increases in the presence of alcohols, glycerol, chlorides, sulphates, nitrates, oxalates, citrates, tartrates, some sugars, etc.

(4) It diminishes in the presence of acids (not very dilute).

Now turning to the causes that appear to determine the period of induction, it would be observed that it is due to the combined influence of the following factors:—

1. Influence of successive stages in the reaction (p. 542).
2. Change in temperature.
3. Catalytic influence of added substances.

Successive reactions. It would readily be understood that chemical reactions, occurring in successive stages, would have a period of induction during which time the successive reactions take place inside the system. "This is a necessary consequence of the law of mass action. The duration of the period depends on the relative magnitude of the velocity constants of the intermediate reactions." (Mellor, "Comprehensive Treatise in Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry" 1922, Vol. II, p. 185).

Since the velocity of a chemical reaction is proportional to the mass of the reacting substances, the belated appearance of the cuprous hydride or chloride respectively, which is the period of induction, corresponds to the time necessary for the successive

reactions to take place before precipitation commences. The successive stages in which both the reactions take place have already been indicated.

Temperature. It has been shown that an increase of temperature causes diminution in the period of induction. This is due to the following causes:—

1. An increase of temperature increases the velocity of the intermediate reactions which would, therefore, result in decrease in the period of induction.

2. It increases ionisation with a resultant increase in the velocity of the intermediate reactions and thus diminishes the period of induction.

Influence of added substances. The influence of added substances, (*e.g.*, alcohols, glycerol, salts and acids) appears to be of a catalytic nature. As regards the action of acids the diminution of the period of induction is evidently due to the presence of a large number of hydrogen ions which act catalytically.

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